

Soil Organic Matter on Capillarity Control and Seepage Loss

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Seepage causes water logging and the irrigable land becomes useless for cultivation specially in regions where there is chance of increase of soil salinity. This may be minimised to some extent by application of humic acid, a soil organic matter, which imparts water repellency to soil and exerts influence on capillarity.

FROM thermodynamical approach coupled with the theory of diffusion, it is now an established fact that movement of water in a soil depends on (a) capillarity, (b) diffusivity, and (c) permeability. Capillarity is responsible for storage of water in soil. According to Buckingham¹ the flow of water through a soil is comparable to the flow of heat through a metal bar. The driving force or the capillary current is because of the difference in attraction for water between two sections of the soil that are not equally moist. The energy relationship is termed as capillary potential (ψ) which is now widely denoted as Matric Potential, and is defined as the work required to move a unit mass of water against capillary forces in a column of soil. Since the capillary forces work in upward direction to hold water, therefore Matric Potential is written with a negative sign. Measurement of surface tension value, in fact, gives the idea regarding the capillarity potential or Matric Potential.

The object of the investigation is to explore the possibilities of checking the seepage loss by the application of humic acid (H.A.) isolated from soil. For this, capillarity test was performed on soil using H.A.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was performed with natural and microbial humic acid (H.A.). The natural one was extracted from alluvial soil, West Bengal (Chinsura farm soil, 0.15 cm depth) by the standard procedure² and the microbial ones were synthesized by two different fungus streptomyces (SpC₇) and strachybotrys atra (StA) according to Martin, Richard and Haider³. Standard sand of B.S. (100) was used as the soil media for the present experiment. The dry powdered organic matters of varying weights were mixed thoroughly in presence of water with definite weight of sand so as to have 0.1%, 0.2%, 0.3%, 0.4% and 0.5% by weight of O.M. contaminations. These were now carefully dried. A graduated cylinder of 60 cm length and 7 cm diameter whose one end was fitted with a wirenet to place the O.M. sand mixtures was now filled with those samples carefully so as to ensure uniformity of filling. It was now placed vertically in an enamelled trough and water was poured in the trough to maintain a definite depth in the column. Immediately after pouring water, stopwatch was started and rise of water in the cylinder containing the sample was noted after each 15 secs until the rise of water stopped. This experiment was repeated in all the cases. Surface tension of 0.1%, 0.2%, 0.3%, 0.4% and 0.5% organic matter solutions were determined using stalagmometer.

Results and Discussion

The experimental results recorded in the Table 2 show that the height (ht) of capillary rise decreases with increase of O.M. Concentration upto 0.3% and beyond that it again increases irrespective of the nature of O.M. used. The decrease is to some extent more rapid in case of sand-H.A. mixture.

TABLE 1—SURFACE TENSION (S.T.) OF O. M SOLUTIONS

Nature of O. M	% of O. M by wt	S.T (dynes/cm)
H.A.	0.0	79.7
	0.1	77.8
	0.2	76.9
	0.3	76.2
	0.4	76.7
	0.5	77.9
H.A.(SpC ₇)	0.0	79.7
	0.1	77.6
	0.2	76.6
	0.3	75.8
	0.4	76.4
	0.5	77.1
H.A.(StA)	0.0	79.6
	0.1	77.1
	0.2	75.8
	0.3	75.0
	0.4	75.9
	0.5	76.9

